

“Awareness Towards Education Among Students In Delhi NCR”

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Abstract

Over the past decades, technology has made a significant contribution to the development of education and has had a profound effect on school education in India. The Government of India has placed appropriate emphasis on Education (ET) technology in successive national education policies. Until 2019, Edtech did not attract enough funding, but the Covid-19 epidemic accelerated online learning and gave birth to a few EdTech startups in India and around the world. These Edtech companies have been around for almost two decades and promised a bright future in education. It is believed that education is one of the main sources of prosperity for millions of people living in Asian countries.

However, the main method of delivery did not change fundamentally in the long run. Although some institutions have begun to use digital technology, the education sector is slow to embrace and implement the new age technology in its system. The same was true on the basis that the digital education system could eliminate the jobs of a few teachers, at least in school education. This current study aims to map out the current state of EdTech in India and their prospects. The current study also examines the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges (SWOC) linked to Edtech companies after covid-19.

CROWDFUNDING OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY STARTUPS IN INDIA

Edtech companies that accumulate sponsorship on social media are ten pennies right now. We wanted to be able to dig a little deeper and understand how investor react to edtech programs on these sites.

Crowdfunding is a fundraiser where creators of an idea or business or community project ask for financial support from strangers who want to participate by developing small amounts of money to get the latest prize. Remember that crowdfunding only helps sponsorships, but not the process of creating or distributing sponsored product or services.

While crowdfunding brings as the new thing the fact that it is done online, it is not a new approach. It already existed before the advent of the internet and came from sponsoring and promoting projects by the community. Undoubtedly it was crowdfunding "offline". It was a gift from the French people to the American people and represented freedom.

Crowdfunding also stands for that freedom, in the sense that it allows for retirement to depend on the many institutions that have so far hindered the efficiency of entrepreneurs when presenting their own projects. It is part of a business-based practice among people, from which consultants are removed.

TYPES OF CROWDFUNDING

According to the European Association of crowdfunding, there are four types of crowdfunding-

Reward-Based Crowdfunding-

This crowdfunding method is probably the most popular and comes in forums like Kickstarter and Indiegogo. With reward-based fundraising, people can promise money for creative projects, new pieces of technology, or any other product or service. What makes it so successful is that sponsors who accumulate projects in the forums receive benefits or rewards when they donate their money to the right projects or companies.

While it may seem easy enough to post a project online, there are many attempts at it before it can successfully receive funding. Getting thousands of people to contribute to a project requires the same if not extra attention, planning, and acting like any other successful marketing or fundraising campaign.

Equity Crowdfunding-

Award-based crowd sponsors make donations to win awards and complete satisfaction of helping companies achieve their goals. On the other hand, equity crowd sponsors provide companies with operating capital to acquire a company piece. Usually, to get a business down or to give it a lot of money, entrepreneurs often turn to foreign investors for more money.

Equity crowdfunding allows investors to participate in the company's limited ownership because each of them receives a share of the company and a percentage of the profits. This can be beneficial in the beginning because it is a quick way to earn money. However, this can be difficult when it comes to legal requirements. This is because it allows for a large number of equal investors in the business. As a result, business owners may lose some of their power.

Donation-Based Crowdfunding-

GoFundMe is an excellent example of a platform that uses donor crowdfunding. This type of crowdfunding is often used by non-profit organizations that require donations to raise funds for their causes. Most donors who donate money for these platforms usually do not expect to give back and donate to the topic or organization they support. In all cases, the ROI (return on investment) arises from the personal satisfaction that comes from contributing to the project.

Peer-to-Peer Lending-

In the past, peer lending meant borrowing money from loved ones to business. However, these days, platforms like Lending Club and Prosper have emerged to use the same concept in fundraising. This allows beginners to access finances outside of conventional lending channels.

The 3 main pillars of current crowdfunding are:

1- Creator.

It is the facilitator of the idea or project for which funding is requested. It should be a person who creates self-confidence, so anonymity is not recommended. It should be a person or group that has ownership on social media.

2- A project or idea.

Being a new project (providing a different solution to the problem), a new one (without market presence) and generating value in the world (that it was actually claimed by someone other than the real creator). It should be transmitted or communicated in video format and, if possible, in prototype.

2- Refund or reward.

It is beneficial. There must be a clear relationship between the amount requested and the amount provided as a refund. It is something that determines the market itself. For this reason, it is recommended that you look at at least 12 crowdfunding campaigns before designing your own, to see what rewards are offered, what type, and how much money is being requested. The reward can be a kiss, a percentage of the company or the project itself to be presented, but it should always be a refund of the requested amount. The campaign usually has several reward levels, depending on the different prices requested (for example, a reward of 5 euros, one of 15 euros, one of 25 euros, and so on).

EDTECH MARKET

Edtech market is becoming increasingly complex and flexible and constantly changing with stakeholders such as retailers, technology platform providers; content developers; teachers; students; institutions such as clients, investors, regulators, governments. Edtech market is diverse, with big players like Byjus and small beginners trying their hands in India. The availability of cheap internet connectivity with reasonable bandwidth through digital forums increases daily demand. These Edtech companies promise the delivery of quality education and easy access at a low cost compared to traditional classroom delivery environments. Covid-19 pandemic, while playing havoc on the life of people, also planted the seeds of the digital learning model in the education sector.

The influence of such Edtech companies in the ever-increasing digital space in the education sector is growing day by day, especially in the post-Covid-19 pandemic. The governments and its regulators were waiting for a long time to introduce large-scale technical innovations through education technology to scale up the outreach and improve the gross enrollment ratio (GER) in schools and colleges/universities. They want to transform the teaching-learning process in the education sector and introduce analytical tools to evaluate the investment made in the education sector. The unexpected impetus to Edtech post-Covid-19 brought several challenges to the stakeholders viz. learners, educators, administrators, governments, and employers in various forms in the admission process, access to physical books, face-to-face interaction with teachers and their peer groups. However, the Edtech companies quickly stepped in at the early stage of remote learning. They provided online solutions by helping the institutions to hold online admissions tests, proctored examinations, and digital content in a collaborative role.

FUNDING OF EDTECH START-UPS ECO SYSTEM

India has been constantly climbing the ladder of innovation and the first ecosystem. Today the Indian Edtech start up ecosystem uses state-of-the-art technology to attract the attention of the industry, emerging capitalists, corporations, and governments. Many of them have successfully used prototypes to attract investment. They have successfully attracted large-scale investment, which encourages continued growth of the sector, especially during and after the Covid-19 epidemic. The Edtech industry provides angels and corporate investors with the opportunity to earn a significant financial return while helping the cause of education in the country.

The entry point for Edtech companies in India is to use one or more combinations of (a) Shared Business; (b) cooperation; (c) Franchise; As the industry reveals, of the top ten companies that attracted investment from 5 million to 200 million by 2020, eight were in the test preparation phase, one in K-12, skills development, business solution, and certification. . Access to higher education is still lacking. Financial business education finance globally The 2021 analytical report published by HolonIQ in early 2022 shows that Chinese EdTech investment is falling with impressive investment growth in the US and Europe. From \$ 1 billion in 2014, Indian Edtech startups reached \$ 3.8 billion by 2021 and positioned it near the United States (\$ billion). Europe (\$ 3.0 billion) is the third most popular region, followed by China (\$ 2.7 billion). China's investment started at \$ 0.6 billion in 2014 and grew to \$ 10.2 billion by 2020 and suddenly dropped to \$ 2.7 billion by 2021. In the case of the United States, there is a significant increase from \$ 2.5 billion by 2020 to \$ 8.3 billion. Europe's growth is almost identical to that of India, which started at \$ 1 billion in 2014 and reached \$ 3.0 billion by 2021. India has now become the leading investor in Asia at the beginning of Edtech, surpassing Europe, yet the sector is not much different.

EDTECH ADOPTION IN POST COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Many schools and institutions of higher learning had switched to digital to offer education for the first time, and, in the middle of the night, it happened. However, it cannot be said that moving from offline mode to offline was a hassle because there were no participants, i.e.. teachers, students, or staff, trained to manage their new delivery delivery tools. Many have tried to replicate classes and laboratories to better understand their students at their level with the tools available. Many institutions have begun to invest heavily in technology-driven programs such as hardware, software content, and training to create online and integrated systems in order to improve efficiency and overcome problems of access to education in remote areas. In order to enhance and support modern teaching, there is an urgent need for the integration of classrooms, seminars, and conference rooms with Edtech-based services once students or students return to campuses.

Today, all institutions predict that visual learning will not end even after this epidemic next year. Practical learning with the help of Edtech companies charges a new chapter in human learning history. Rethinking how to bring educational resources to the institutional environment. However, the challenge lies in how the education ecosystem is prepared to embrace the digital transformation opportunities brought about by the epidemic.

In contrast, there are a number of challenges that Edtech companies are currently facing. There is a delay in obtaining a patent under the Indian Copyright Act and the Patent Office. On average, it takes 3 to 4 months to complete a certificate.

There is a lack of digital readiness in institutions. Most of these institutions are funded by government agencies such as the School Office or Higher Education at the District Government level and at the Central level through the University Grants Commission. The lack of strong IT and connectivity / bandwidth, especially in rural, back-and-forth areas, is also hampering the growth of Edtech companies in India. The Edtech market in India is very competitive, and it is crowded and operates in a small area. Of the 4500 Edtech initiatives operating in this field, only a few have achieved promotions and e-profit profits, taxes, depreciation, amortization (EBITDA) margins.

The governing bodies in the higher education sector do not support Edtech companies that are replacing online degree programs in partnership with HEIs. India is a multilingual country, Edtech donations need to be customized, and companies may incur additional costs and eliminations for regional players. Most companies focus exclusively on the K-12 market segment preparation test, which leaves the competition for higher education. There is a lack of variance in the supply market because the cost could not determine the cost. There is a growing need for players to focus on classification without raising the bar. Most Edtech startups are unable to keep the customer afloat, leading to failure on delivery. There is a lack of funding for access to more expensive digital programs to facilitate online learning and sustainability.

Once they reach their target, they reduce marketing costs by 40 to 50 percent. India's education system continues to be a test subject due to public pressure to do well in competitive exams to get into university education. Adapting to a new digital culture in schools and HEIs may take longer. With the exception of a few, most of the investors in the EdTech field are specialists or regular business funds, and many of the most heavily funded companies are located in areas where these investors are beginning to seek out. A growing number of IPOs (First Public Offerings) are listed by VCs or discarded by their corporate owners. Therefore, there is a need for public funding in the EdTech sector.

The public sector in India has been instrumental in bringing about digital revolution in every possible way, and the government is investing heavily in such programs. In recent years all governments and founders have invested heavily in education. It has, in a sense, enabled Edtech companies to gain power. Millions of users have started using in-app learning during the Covid-19 era. "Flexible and personalized learning is becoming more common among teenagers and school children. Many urban schools are starting to use this technology, and young teachers are increasingly coming to run the learning process.

CROWD FUNDING EDUCATION

Today, there could be a various reasons to consider crowd funding ; it could be entrepreneurial ventures, social cause, higher studies, music albums or videos, gigs and festivals, publishing books, mega events or college projects. There are different forms of crowd funding available . It could be reward based, loan based or equity based. However, in India, the most popular way of securing funds, is the rewards or returns based funding. On being questioned as to their willingness to support educational cause, the respondents were of the view point that they would surely to the of furtherance of education. On being asked about the factors influencing their decision for contributing towards education, the respondents felt that they would prefer financing students who are from weak financial backgrounds and performing well academically.

CROWD SOURCING EDUCATION

Education to help more people and learning is not limited to campus boundaries. Information on all types of courses and courses is now available online. This wealth of information comes from the crowd and can be replanted in the classroom or beyond. Visual classes have gained importance these days. Online courses are becoming more and more popular. Many US universities also have their own forums to encourage students and academics to apply for financial assistance for their projects, and it is becoming increasingly common in the UK.

UK.

CROWDS FOR CROWDFUNDING

Very popular: People donate money to get something (reward). It is governed by the rules of e-commerce and data privacy. Funds are requested to receive prizes that are consistent with all budgets. It can be digital or virtual prizes. Customers, who show that the project makes sense in the market, are wanted. The mass rewards campaign helps to ensure the project, to grow it, to see how difficult it is to reach the target audience. Donors know that a product or service is a model and that it will take time for them to develop a real product. Usually, these people give a lot of feedback instead of how they want that product. Divided into:

Reward crowdfunding "all or nothing".

If the requested amount is not met, no fee is available.

Therefore, it is recommended that you request the minimum required for the project to proceed.

Reward crowdfunding "everything is important".

All euros that go into the campaign are brought to the creator of the project.

With this type of campaign there is a problem with confidence: Once we have said we need an "X" of value to put a job, we have to show how we will put the job if we get less money.

Therefore, it applies to very modular projects.

MOST CROWDFUNDED PLATFORM IN EDUCATIONAL SITES

1. **DonorsChoose-** This nonprofit crowdfunding platform makes it easy to raise money for any classroom in need of funds online.
2. **GiveCampus-** Give Campus partners with colleges to help students, alumni, parents, and faculty launch fundraisers for school-related projects.
3. **Piggybackr-** is a US crowdfunding website for students and youth teams to fundraise for their schools, projects, and causes online. It is compliant with the American Children's Online Privacy Protection Act, meaning that children as young as 5 can run fundraising projects on-line. Backers of projects can post public comments, but cannot communicate directly with the children posting projects. Children under the age of 13 must have parental involvement with their projects.
4. **GoFundMe-** is an American for-profit crowdfunding platform that allows people to raise money for events ranging from life events such as celebrations and graduations to challenging circumstances like accidents and illnesses. From 2010 to the beginning of 2020, over \$9 billion has been raised on the platform, with contributions from over 120 million donors
5. **FundRazr-** is a free crowdfunding and online fundraising platform released in 2009. FundRazr operates internationally in 35+ countries with the largest markets being United States, Canada, United Kingdom and Australia. It allows users to run a wide-range of

crowdfunding campaigns by creating fundraising pages and sharing it via social media, messaging apps, email and more to raise money for over 100 types of causes such as nonprofit, medical care, education, community help, poverty alleviation, arts, memorials, and animal rescue causes.

6. **Fundly**-Fundly is a crowdfunding site for online fundraising. It allows non-profits, charities, politics, clubs, schools, teams, churches, and other causes to raise money online from friends, family, colleagues, donors, and other supporters via email, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google, and social media networks.

7. **Classy**- Classy is a software company and online fundraising platform designed for nonprofit organizations. Headquartered in San Diego, California, Classy was founded by CEO Scot Chisholm, Pat Walsh, and Marshall Peden in 2006, originally to host fundraising events that benefit charities.

CONCLUSION

The growth motivation for Edtech eco-system in India lies in four factors - (a) the number of young people; (b) Increase parental income; (c) the low cost of internet data; and (d) cheap mobile learning gadgets. It is estimated that smart phone users will double in 2025 from 500 million by 2020. Admittedly, the implementation of Edtech has disrupted part of training and exam preparation, but they have not yet touched the core of the value chain of education. The introduction of digital technology into the education system can serve as a parallel and will not replace the traditional education system. Edtech companies should keep the truth in mind when designing their offerings.

Although the Covid-19 epidemic has accelerated the transformation of digital technology into the education sector, consistent efforts must be made by Edtech companies to keep interest alive among stakeholders. It is possible with ongoing innovations and new offerings. When the epidemic is over, schools / colleges reopened, normalcy restored; student retention may cause problems in these Edtech forums. Edtech beginners face complex challenges such as low customer base, inability to determine the right amount of offerings, lack of diversity, lack of product division, high customer acquisition. Edtech emerging players must use a variety of strategies to survive in a crowded environment.

They have to rely heavily on extension, innovation, integration, approval of student results, and fragmentation. Edtech beginners should use Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) extensively to provide better user experience and bring realistic learning features that can be brought to the place of a traditional, offline classroom. Edtech beginners need to focus on acquiring new digital skills to prepare students for future roles in the job market. Diversity in the nearby Edtech segment is also a good option for an extended survival company. There are successful beginners who participate in student learning and teaching notes. MOOCs are also another way to use higher education and business students. Now is the time for higher education institutions to establish good relations with Edtech companies. The level of contribution of their program is not refined but improved to achieve growth and goals. The future of the study space will be small in the visual infrastructure and large in the digital space, and Edtech could play a role in empowering GER development. Edtech is expected to play a role in motivating and helping institutions to improve their studies and meet the needs of hungry young students.

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